

1 **An experimental immune regimen for treatment of lung metastasis in breast cancer.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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- 8 1. Lung metastasis occurs in some significant fraction of patients diagnosed with breast cancer of any molecular subtype.
- 9 2. Lung metastasis will inevitably follow disease recurrence (“relapse”) in a fraction of patients with breast cancer.
- 10 3. Lung metastasis is difficult to treat and frequently results in death.
- 11 4. We recently demonstrated that the immune receptor Igsf9b is activated in the lymph nodes prior to dissemination to the lungs, and in the lungs following metastasis to the lungs in patients with metastatic breast cancer.
- 12 5. Treatment failure in patients with breast cancer is associated with metastasis to distant sites including the liver, lungs, the skeletal system (bones) and brain (CNS).
- 13 6. We recently utilized a cohort over nearly 3,000 humans to study, at the systems level and on a population scale, the effect of tumor gene expression across the transcriptome, on distant metastasis-free survival.
- 14 7. Among the top 0.1% most differentially expressed genes across the lung metastatic transcriptome that were up-regulated and thus could serve as a traditional therapeutic target, virtually all lacked a significant influence on distant metastasis-free survival in humans.
- 15 8. Igsf9b, and a second molecule, a lung surfactant protein, SFTPA2, possessed strong correlations between tumor expression of the gene and metastasis to a distant site.
- 16 9. We suspect SFTPA2 likely functions as a tissue-restricted antigen to silence tumor immunosurveillance in the lungs during effective metastasis.
- 17 10. PD1-PDL1 checkpoint inhibitors like Pembrolizumab (Keytruda) may be considered augmenting agents in chemotherapeutic regimens that target activation in the immune system.
- 18 11. We previously presented a hypothesis that argued tumor necrotic or apoptotic activity can enhance adaptive immune responses involving CD8+ CTLs (as well as hybrid innate-adaptive responses involving NK cells and gamma-delta T-cells).
- 19 12. Antibody drug conjugate agents combine a toxic payload that served as a poison for a cancer cell with a monoclonal antibody that detects some specific aspect of a tumor. Thus, we hypothesize delivering pembrolizumab (Keytruda) together with a Trop-2 (TACSTD2) antibody ADCC (Sacituzumab govitecan) will augment any chemotherapeutic regimen targeting immune activation status in the metastasis or primary tumor.
- 20 13. We present here a Compassionate Use Protocol request for administration of monoclonal antibody cocktail consisting of an antibody that targets Igsf9b in conjunction with an antibody that targets the tissue-restricted antigen SFTPA2 (together with pembrolizumab and Sacituzumab govitecan) in patients who have developed lung metastasis following:

- primary treatment failure
- relapse following partial (PR) or complete response (CR).

Supporting and relevant data follow here:

We studied total transcription in lung metastases and in the primary tumor to identify genes activated during metastasis to the lung.

Results

Figure 1: IGSF9B is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

- I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
22997	1.57E-08	0.551	-5.653817	-3.1132813	163.72	IGSF9B	21/22,997	99.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *IGSF9B* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of IGSF9B changed more than 99% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of IGSF9B messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of IGSF9B during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of IGSF9B likely defined the lung metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

1
2 **Results**

3 **Figure 2:** SFTPA2 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

4 Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

5 *n*=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

6 *n*=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
729238	8.35E-10	1.628	-6.138081	-9.9914569	1391.46	SFTPA2	12/22,997	99.9

8 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung
9 metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell
10 adhesion molecule, encoded by SFTPA2 in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (Chart
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12 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank").
13 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of SFTPA2 messenger RNA in lung
14 metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of SFTPA2 during disease progression and dissemination in
15 breast cancer.

16 Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of SFTPA2 likely defined the lung
17 metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.
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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 (9) for the tumor transcriptome study presented as evidence in this Compassionate Use Request. We conducted this study by measuring total transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods. When data for GSE56493 is not present, it failed to satisfy validation, and was consulted but omitted.